

INTEGRATION OF HYDROGEOLOGICAL VARIABLES IN RANDOM FOREST MODELS FOR DOWNSCALING OF TWS ANOMALIES IN CHILE

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ABSTRACT – The coarse spatial resolution of Terrestrial Water Storage (TWS) data provided by the GRACE/GRACE-FO mission limits its applicability in regional water resource management studies. This work implements a Random Forest-based statistical downscaling model to increase the spatial resolution of TWS to 0.25° in the Chilean territory. The model is interconnected with hydrogeological, geospatial and temporal variables. The results show that the inclusion of spatiotemporal predictors improves significantly the model's predictive ability ($R=0.74$, $RMSE=1.97$ cm). The validation within situ observations of 485 wells shows positive correlations ($R>0.5$) in 60% of cases. This approach highlights the potential of machine learning to increase the regional applicability of GRACE data.

1 INTRODUCTION

Terrestrial Water Storage (TWS) reflects the sum of surface water and groundwater, including rivers, lakes, snow, and soil moisture (Giroto & Rodell, 2019; Humphrey et al., 2023). Since 2002, the Gravity Recovery and Climate Experiment (GRACE) mission and its successor, GRACE-FO, have provided global coverage of Terrestrial Water Storage (TWS) at a spatial resolution of approximately 350 km (over 160,000 km²) (Rodell et al., 2009). However, this scale is insufficient for local studies (Ali et al., 2021). Several downscaling methods have been proposed to overcome this limitation, combining GRACE data with high-resolution variables from climate models or data assimilation (Chen et al., 2019; Jyolsna et al., 2021). Among the most successful approaches are machine learning algorithms such as Random Forest, which allow modeling nonlinear relationships between TWS and hydroclimatic predictors.

In Chile, sustainable water management faces challenges associated with prolonged droughts and aquifer overexploitation (Donoso, 2021; Vargas-Payera et al., 2023). The availability of high-spatial-resolution TWS data could contribute to informed decision-making. Thus, the objective of this study is to develop a 0.25° downscaling model for GRACE-derived TWS using Random Forest and validate its predictions against well-level observations.

2 DATA AND METHODS

2.1 Study Area

Chile extends from 18°S to 56°S, covering a diverse climate and geology that includes arid, semi-arid, Mediterranean, and temperate zones. The study area is defined between 18°S and 40°S, where the main aquifers exploited for human and agricultural consumption are located. The Andes Mountain range dominates the eastern topography, while the intermediate depressions and the Coastal Mountain Range influence precipitation distribution and recharge.

2.2 Data

We used data from GRACE, GLDAS, TRMM, NASADEM and DGA groundwater level records (see Table 1).

Table 1 – Summary of variables, data sources, and spatial resolution.

Variables	Data source	Resolution
Terrestrial Water Storage (mascon)	GRACE (JPL)	0.50°x0.50°
Precipitation	TRMM version 7	0.25°x0.25°
Hydrogeological variables	GLDAS-NOAH v2.1	0.25°x0.25°
Elevation	NASADEM HGT v001	30 m
Static well levels	National Water Bureau (DGA-Chile)	-

The GRACE mission provides monthly Total Water Storage Anomaly (TWSA) data as spatially distributed samples, with resolutions ranging from 1° to 0.25°, depending on the processing level. (Ali et al., 2024). Although the effective resolution of GRACE data is approximately 300–400 km (Ferreira et al., 2024), this study employs monthly GRACE and GRACE-FO data processed by the Jet Propulsion Laboratory (JPL) at a resolution of 0.5°, covering the period 2003–2022.

The Global Land Data Assimilation System (GLDAS) combines land surface models and observational data to produce estimates of hydrologic variables to the nearest 0.25° per month since 2000. It includes precipitation, soil moisture, snow, and evapotranspiration (Beaudoin & Rodell, 2019).

The Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission (TRMM) provides monthly precipitation estimates at 0.25° from 1998 to 2019, based on microwaves and calibrated with surface stations.

NASADEM is a digital elevation model derived from the SRTM (30 m) reprocessed by NASA JPL in 2020 (NASA JPL, 2020). It provides altitude above mean sea level and allows the representation of topographic gradients.

The official database of Chile's General Water Department (DGA) contains monthly series of static levels from 573 wells between 2000 and 2020, with information on geographic location, depth, and measurement date.

2.3 Statistical downscaling of Terrestrial Water Storage (TWS)

We adopted a Random Forest-based (RF) statistical downscaling approach for the implementation of the downscaling model at a spatial resolution of 0.25° , in accordance with the proposal by Breiman (2001). RF has been used successfully in previous experiments, e.g., Ali et al. (2021), Chen et al. (2019), and Jyolsna et al. (2021).

The applied procedure is based on the idea of establishing a statistical mapping between temporal variations in TWS derived from GRACE and a set of higher-resolution hydrogeological and geospatial predictors, including variables such as soil moisture, surface runoff, snow water equivalent, vegetation water content, terrain elevation, evapotranspiration, monthly accumulated precipitation, and temperature. These variables were previously aggregated onto a regular grid coinciding with the target resolution of 0.25° .

The model was trained using monthly TWS data at a resolution of 0.5° , under the hypothesis that the inferred statistical relationship between TWS anomalies and hydrogeological and geospatial predictors remains valid with increasing spatial resolution (Rodell et al., 2009; Humphrey et al., 2017). This assumption is consistent with other studies that have employed downscaling techniques to convert integrated satellite signals into local estimates of hydrological variables (Long et al., 2017).

Hyperparameter tuning of the RF model (number of trees, maximum depth, and number of candidate variables per split) was performed using a grid search approach. In this process, a model was built for each hyperparameter combination within a predefined search space, its performance evaluated using k-fold cross-validation and using the minimum root mean square error (RMSE) of the validation set as a selection criterion (Probst et al., 2019).

Model performance is evaluated from a comparison between the model predictions (y_i) and observations (x_i) for a set of n test values. For this purpose, four statistical indices are used: the root mean square error (RMSE), the correlation coefficient (R), the mean absolute error (MAE) and the Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency (NSE). The RMSE measures the average distance between predictions and observations, the MAE measures the average magnitude of the errors, the R measures the strength and direction of the relationship, while the NSE is used to assess the model's ability to reproduce observed variability. These indices are calculated respectively as:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - y_i)^2}{n}} \quad (1)$$

$$R = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2}} \quad (2)$$

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - x_i| \right) \quad (3)$$

$$NSE = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - x_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2} \quad (4)$$

Once the model was trained, monthly groundwater storage (GWS) predictions were generated at a spatial resolution of 0.25° . To obtain coarse-scale groundwater storage variations, contributions from other terrestrial water reserves, specifically soil moisture, snow water equivalent, and vegetation water, were subtracted from the high-resolution TWS predictions. The latter were extracted from GLDAS at an equivalent resolution.

Finally, the monthly GWS time series generated by the model were compared with static water level records observed in an independent set of monitoring wells distributed throughout the study region. This validation procedure quantifies the model's predictive capacity and assesses its applicability.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study evaluated the performance of downscaling models for TWSA estimated by GRACE using Random Forest algorithms with different sets of predictor variables. Two configurations were trained and compared: a model based exclusively on hydrological variables and another that also incorporated spatiotemporal predictors (latitude, longitude, altitude, month, and year).

Figure 2 – Performance of the best models. a) Model trained with hydrological features, b) Model trained with hydrological and spatiotemporal features.

Figure 2a shows the dispersion between observed TWS values (GRACE) and those predicted by the model using only hydrological variables. This model achieved a coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.46 and a Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency (NSE) index of 0.46, demonstrating a moderate ability to capture the spatial and temporal variability of the anomalies. The mean absolute errors (MAE) and root mean square errors (RMSE) were 3.90 cm and 5.52 cm, respectively, while the slope of the linear regression was relatively low (0.43), indicating that the model tended to underestimate the observed extreme TWS values. These results suggest that, while hydrological information provides an appreciable level of explanatory power, it is not sufficient to reproduce the full signal of the anomalies with high accuracy.

In contrast, the model that integrated spatiotemporal variables showed substantially better performance (Figure 2b). The R^2 and NSE increased to 0.93, the slope of the linear regression increased to 0.85, and errors were significantly reduced (RMSE = 1.98 cm and MAE = 1.24 cm). This increase in predictive ability highlights the importance of geospatial and temporal information in capturing regional and seasonal patterns in TWS variability. These results highlight the importance of incorporating spatial and temporal factors, unlike other studies that only used hydrological variables (e.g., Chen et al., 2019).

Figure 3 – Feature importance ranking.

The relative importance (Gini coefficient) of each predictor in the combined model is summarized in Figure 3. Temporal (year and month) and spatial (latitude) variables were the most relevant, followed by soil moisture and vegetation water storage. This pattern suggests that multiannual trends and geographic location are determining factors in the dynamics of the TWS in Chile. The high contribution of temporal variables could be associated with the strong influence of interannual phenomena (e.g., El Niño-Southern Oscillation) that modulate water availability in the region. Furthermore, the importance of soil moisture and evapotranspiration highlights the importance of surface water-atmosphere exchange processes in determining the observed fluctuations.

Figure 4 – Original TWS and downscaled TWS models. a) March 2010 and b) October 2019

Downscaling revealed substantial changes, highlighting the model ability to capture more detailed spatial patterns compared to the original TWS data (Figure 4). When comparing the simulated groundwater storage (GWS) derived from TWS data with in-situ measurements from 485 wells distributed throughout the study region, 60% showed positive correlations ($R > 0.5$). Of note were LAS MAITAS ($R = 0.64$) in Arica, JICA-5 ($R = 0.82$) in Tarapacá, ALGARROBAL ($R = 0.71$) in Coquimbo, ASENTAMIENTO CHACABUCO ($R = 0.72$) in the Metropolitan Region, ASENTAMIENTO SAN ISIDRO ($R = 0.55$) in Libertador Bernardo O’Higgins, and ASOC. CANALISTAS BIOBIO SUR ($R = 0.59$) in Biobío. However, at some stations, such as SANTA BARBARA, the correlation was negative, which could indicate local limitations in the model fit. These results are illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5 – Correlation of downscaled GWS time series and static well levels.

4 CONCLUSION

The implementation of a RF based statistical downscaling model proved highly effective in improving the spatial resolution of GRACE-derived total water storage (TWS) data in Chile. Comparatively, these results are according with previous research that has reported significant improvements in downscaling models when including geographic and seasonal variables as key predictors. The significant increase in R^2 and error reduction observed in this study demonstrate that an integrative approach, combining hydroclimatic and spatial data, can substantially improve the reconstruction capacity of TWS satellite signals, even at finer spatial resolution.

In summary, the Random Forest model with hydrological and spatiotemporal variables offered a robust and high-fidelity approach for downscaling TWS anomalies in Chile, showing significant potential for operational applications in hydrological monitoring and water availability studies. However, it is acknowledged that, despite the improvement, the regression slope did not reach unity, suggesting room for improvement in capturing extreme values. Future work could

evaluate the incorporation of additional high-resolution predictors, such as satellite meteorological variables or vegetation indices, as well as the exploration of hybrid models that integrate deep learning to further improve downscaling accuracy.

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